

MATILDE

Migration Impact Assessment to Enhance
Integration and Local Development in
European Rural and Mountain Regions

Summer School

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MATILDE Summer School

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MATILDE Summer School

Theme: **International Migration in Remote Places**

Date: **13-17 June, 2022**

Place: **Bussoleno (Italy)**

Photo 1 A visit to the MATILDE Big Bench, built during Action Research in Bussoleno

Aim, Background and Context

The summer school was organized to **strengthen the link between research, teaching, and learning**, and guide the participants to develop their argumentation and critical analytical thinking about the relevance of international migration to remote places which have been neglected over the last few decades. The aim was to allow the participants to enhance their reflective learning outcomes as they not only benefit directly from the most up-to-date research, but also have an opportunity to bring a contribution to it and take part in the co-production of knowledge. Student participants earned 3 ECTS for completing the program.

Against the **background** of global trends such as urbanization and agglomeration, economic and forced migration flows are also moving outside urban areas. So far, this has largely been perceived as yet another burden for already marginalized territories. The specific needs of rural and mountain regions have been scarcely considered at the time of formulating the governance of migration. If unaddressed, the sentiments of people in 'places that don't matter' risk fuelling an authoritarian, nativist and populist dynamic, rejecting diversity altogether. The main assumption of the Summer School was that **migrations to rural and mountain areas can play an important role for European rural regions**, among the other things, by contributing to revitalization of social and economic local milieu, reducing territorial inequalities and reconfiguring urban-rural interconnections.

The MATILDE International Summer School 2022 therefore aimed at focusing on the discussions revolving around international migration and its challenges and opportunities in remote places, consisting of **four days of lectures, discussions, deliberations, field excursions and artistic performances** led by a distinguished international faculty. The school blended theoretical and empirical discussions along with the case studies participatory action-research from around Europe and even beyond providing the participants with the opportunities to contribute to the knowledge production processes.

The **Summer School took place in Bussoleno**, a small municipality approximately 45 kilometres west of Turin in the foothills of the Susa Valley, Italy. Already an area of immigration from southern Italy after World War II thanks to the jobs offered by the railway and some local businesses, today Bussoleno is seeking a new economic and social vocation. Its territory, bordering France, is crossed by the new high-speed railway line (TAV) Turin-Lyon, against which a large part of the valley's population has been mobilised over the years, for fear of the negative environmental effects. In recent years, the local municipality has received significant flows of international migration, especially from North Africa and Eastern Europe, attracted by the low cost of housing. Furthermore, Bussoleno is on the route of irregular migration to France, via the surrounding Alpine passes: the town hosts initiatives to support migrants in transit, starting with the local Red Cross centre, where the school was hosted.

Photo 2 A hike along the route of irregular migration to France, photo by Alberto Bertone

Implementation and Evaluation

The activities of the summer school took place as planned in the official programme, with minor adjustments to give more space to deliberation among the participants who came from different disciplines, occupations, civil society organisations, international organisations, and academia.

All but one of the **lectures were given in person**, ensuring a high level of direct interaction between lecturers and students. Participants showed a **high level of engagement** in all the proposed activities, with continuous discussions during the lectures, questions, remarks, and valuable reflections, expressed also on the basis of their own background, as reacting to the solicitations provided by the lecturers.

Photo 3 Lectures at the Red Cross Centre, photo by Alberto Bertone

The presence of many MATILDE researchers fostered a renewed **intellectual exchange** between colleagues and participants, in a very friendly and collaborative atmosphere, thanks to the location and local occasions of informal meetings.

The **involvement in the school of artists/performers**, such as Thomson, and photographers, such as Akimenko and Bertone, also provided an opportunity for a dialogue between scientific knowledge and an artistic view of the reality of migration.

The **public events** planned, such as the inauguration of the photo exhibition in the centre of Bussoleno or Thomson's performance at the Red Cross, attracted a local audience also from outside the school and ensured the school's visibility in the Susa Valley media. This visibility of the MATILDE project as a whole was also favoured by the active involvement of various territorial actors, starting with the presence at the school of the vice-mayor of the Metropolitan City of Turin, Mr. Suppo, and members of the Bussoleno administration and the local Red Cross.

Photo 4 Public events were also an opportunity to visit local landmarks, photo by Graziano Bezzolato

The organisation of lectures and other complementary activities at the **Red Cross Centre**, which also hosts a number of refugees and constitutes a fundamental pole of reception and civil protection in the Susa Valley, offered the participants the opportunity to get to know this type of structure and its methods of intervention up close, in line with the topic of the school and the MATILDE project. At the same time, the **excursions in the area** – to the abandoned village of Falcimagna and along the path of irregular emigration to France – fostered direct and place-based knowledge of the topics discussed, thanks to a full immersion in the

The selected group of **participants** (in total 30 people: 28 in-person, 2 online, out of more than 100 applications received by the organisers) was decidedly diverse in terms of expertise, background, and affiliation. The selected group represented a **variety of disciplines** (sociology, anthropology, geography, international relations, migration studies, etc.), **different geographical origins** (Europe, Middle East, Caucasian Asia, Latin America), and **affiliations, both universities/research institutions** (as PhD students and post doc/junior researchers) **and NGOs and associations** active on the side of migrants' inclusion in marginalised areas (project managers, officers, volunteers). **The majority of participants were female** (24).

Regarding the **evaluation of the school, the participants** filled out an anonymous questionnaire. The participants rated both the organisation of the school – including the complementary activities (excursions, performances, etc.) – and the content and modalities of the lectures. In particular, the topics that awoke most interest were the relationship between immigration and the development of rural/remote areas, populism in remote places, bordering/debordering processes and methodologies for conducting participatory action-research in marginalised territories. A detailed follow-up discussion with the Work Package Leader Group to address the feedback received has been organised.

With respect to the **follow-up of the summer school**, many participants expressed a desire to stay in touch, among themselves and with the lecturers: therefore, a shared address book was created, and exchanges and interconnections are being facilitated. Several participants – in particular PhD students and post docs – requested guidance for their research work from

the lecturers, also asking for the possibility of revising their thesis work or offering theoretical/methodological insights for their work. Finally, some participants have already written or will write short end-of-school essays, in the form of blogposts, to be uploaded on MATILDE's social networks.

Program

Day 1

- Welcome:
Jussi Laine, MATILDE Project Coordinator, UEF, Finland; Bruna Consolini, Mayor of Bussoleno; Jacopo Suppo, Vice-Mayor of the Metropolitan City of Turin; Andrea Membretti, MATILDE, UEF, Finland and University of Torino.
- Introduction: Migration and Local Development in Remote Places
Lecturer: Andrea Membretti, UEF and University of Torino
- Migration, Environment and Climate Change Nexus: perspectives on migrants' contributions in Italy's mountain areas
Lecturer: Marcella Pasotti (IOM, Focal Point MEARL & Innovation – M&D Unit)
- A Gender Perspective on the Economic and Social Impact of Migration
Lecturer: Susanne Stenbacka, MATILDE, Uppsala University
- Migration processes and patterns: Territorial and social dimensions of migrants' interactions with rural localities
Lecturer: Ingrid Machold, MATILDE, Bundesanstalt für Agrarwirtschaft und Bergbauernfragen, Vienna, Austria; Stefan Kordel, MATILDE, Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg
- Public Event: Inauguration of the photo exhibition on migrant workers and newcomers in the Alps of Piedmont and of South Tyrol by the photographers Daria Akimenko and Alberto Bertone. Venue: Casa Ascheri, via Walter Fontan 23, Bussoleno city centre

Day 2

- Methodological and Ethical Aspects of Research with Migrants in Rural and Mountainous Settings
Lecturer: Marika Gruber, MATILDE, Carinthia University of Applied Sciences, Austria and Stefan Kordel, MATILDE, Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg
- Social Impact of Migration in Remote Places
Lecturer: Jussi Laine, MATILDE, UEF, Finland
- Measuring the Economic impact of Migration: Key Concepts, Dimensions and Challenges
Lecturer: Michele Bianchi, MATILDE, University of Parma
- Territorial Polycentrism and Recognition Inequalities: A Metro-Montane Approach
Lecturer: Filippo Barbera, MATILDE, University of Torino
- Excursion to the abandoned village of Falcimagna and presentation of the project related to its regeneration
- Public Event: Opher Thomson: Artistic performance and projection of 'FORREST'.
Venue: Red Cross Centre.

Day 3

- Re/De/Bordering Remoteness: Post-Communist Policies, Experiences, Imaginaries
Lecturer: Anna Krasteva, MATILDE, New Bulgarian University
- Participatory Action Research in Mountain and Rural Communities: Insights from MATILDE Case Studies. Presentation of the MATILDE Manifesto.
Lecturer: Andrea Membretti, MATILDE, UEF and University of Torino; Anna Krasteva, MATILDE, New Bulgarian University
- Populism in Remote Places
Lecturer: Ayhan Kaya, MATILDE, Istanbul Bilgi University
- The Post COVID-19 and The Growing Attractiveness of Internal Regions
Lecturer: Raúl Lardiés-Bosque, MATILDE, University of Zaragoza, Spain

- Closing event: visit to the MATILDE Big Bench (Bussoleno village) and brief presentation of the local action-research activities in Bussoleno
 - Public Event: Video Projection by The Civic Centre (Film On Migrants And Border Crossing In The Alps, E.G. “The Milky Way” . Venue: Red Cross centre.
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Day 4

Full-day excursion to see the route of irregular cross-bordering of migrants from Italy to France and visit some reception initiatives there. Interaction and confrontation with the Red Cross volunteers.